

EFFECTS OF THE FREE MATERNAL HEALTHCARE POLICY ON HOME BIRTH IN
GHANA; THE CASE OF BEKWAI MUNICIPALITY

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ABSTRACT

This mixed-methods study examines the impact of Ghana's Free Maternal Healthcare Policy on maternal healthcare decisions. Utilizing purposive sampling, 182 participants were included in the quantitative section, and 15 individuals contributed to the qualitative section. The results of the quantitative analysis indicate that an overwhelming majority (98.4%) of respondents opted for facility delivery, demonstrating the policy's efficacy. Only 1.6% of participants reported non-facility births. Access to qualified professionals and emergency care were cited as factors influencing decisions to deliver in a facility, further validated by the qualitative findings. While some individuals continue to rely on traditional methods, community opinions and personal experiences significantly shape choices. The decrease in home deliveries can be largely attributed to the policy. The policy's benefits include improved safety, increased access to prenatal care, and the availability of high-quality medical facilities. The financial burden of healthcare is considered a crucial factor in decision-making. An increasing number of individuals are now choosing skilled healthcare providers over traditional birth attendants. The policy promotes the use of modern medical equipment and contemporary healthcare practices. In conclusion, the Free Maternal Health Policy in Ghana has enhanced the safety, accessibility, and affordability of maternal healthcare services.

1.1 Background of the Study

Following Ghana's independence, the government attempted to make health care free by funding them with tax income, but this system was unable to endure due to the country's persistent economic stagnation. A lack of essential medical supplies and equipment as well as a decline in the general level of service provided by Ghana's health sector were caused by the stagnation of the country's economy (Yakubu, 2016). The economic recovery program of the International Monetary Fund and the World Bank was implemented by the PNDC government of Ghana in 1983. This recovery program reduced the lack of medical equipment and supplies, but it was nevertheless accompanied by inequalities in access to care. This occurred as a result of rising health service costs and barriers to care for the underprivileged (Apoya & Marriott, 2011).

The health sector has seen changes since the MDGs were established. Many nations, particularly emerging nations, have subsidized health care, raised health care spending, and created national insurance programs for the general public. However, because of the global economic crisis, some nations were unable to maintain these measures. For instance, in Ghana, during a time of economic hardship, subsidies were eliminated and user fees were implemented at health facilities to lower the balance of payment deficit (Creese & Kutzin, 1997). The NHIS was launched in Ghana in 2003. One objective of the NHIS is to offer a comprehensive package of services, focusing on the nation's underserved and rural areas (Ministry of Health, 2004). Before the introduction of the NHIS, Ghana was operating under a cash-and-carry system, where individuals paid to access health services (Agyepong & Adjei, 2008).

The NHIS offers emergency care, maternity care, oral health care, inpatient care (therapy upon admission), and outpatient care. A medical service known as an outpatient service does not call for an overnight stay in a hospital or other healthcare institution. A hospital or outpatient surgery facility may provide outpatient care (Santiago, 2016). It comprises, among other things, consultations for skin conditions, ulcers, acute respiratory tract infections, and malaria. Medical care that is given in a hospital or other institution and necessitates at least one overnight stay is referred to as inpatient services (Santiago, 2016). It involves general and specialist inpatient care, investigations including laboratory investigations, and accommodation in the general ward, among others. Oral health covers relief for pain, incision and drainage, tooth extraction, and temporary relief. Dental restoration under the NHIS covers services such as simple

amalgam fillings and temporary dressing. The eye care service under the NHIS includes the treatment of refraction, visual fields, keratometry, cataract removal, and eyelid surgery. Maternal care covered under the NHIS includes antenatal care, delivery, cesarean section, and postnatal care. Finally, emergencies include crisis health situations that demand urgent intervention. An example is brain surgery or heart surgery due to accidents (Ministry of Health, 2004).

To provide financial security to Ghana's poor and vulnerable populations and to hasten the process of achieving universal health coverage, an exemption policy was implemented into the National Health Insurance Scheme (NHIS). Free maternal health care and contribution exemptions for children under the age of 18 and the elderly are part of the NHIS's exemption plan. The Ghanaian government implemented a free maternal health care program in 2008 to

increase access to medical treatment for women who are pregnant or have recently given birth. The initiative allowed women to use free family planning services and ambulances, among other things. The Ghanaian government sought to promote childbirth at medical facilities where women would have access to qualified medical personnel and other amenities. According to UNICEF (2013), the effort aimed to lower maternal mortality in Ghana.

1.2 Problem Statement

Ghana's National Health Insurance System (NHIS) established a free maternal health Program in July 2008. As a result of the policy, all expectant women are eligible for free care for the duration of their pregnancy, childbirth, and the first three months following childbirth. One of Ghana's primary initiatives for achieving the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs),

notably the elimination of maternal and infant mortality and the attainment of Universal Health Coverage (UHC). It is unknown whether the policy has produced the anticipated results in every region of Ghana. It has been demonstrated that there are gaps in the implementation of similar policies in other resource-constrained settings because these policies are frequently implemented without proper planning and with an insufficient budget, manpower, and infrastructure. Factors both inside and outside the health system frequently have an impact on implementation, which ultimately has an impact on access to services.

Despite years of government participation in maternal healthcare policy, stillbirth and perinatal death issues in Ghana continue to receive little policy attention. Concerns have been expressed about Ghana's ability to meet the World Health Organization goal of 12 per 1000 live births by 2030 in light of the latest

development. In developing nations, home delivery has been linked to unfavorable outcomes, despite the ongoing debate in developed nations about safety and women's rights to choose between home and hospital delivery (Sorensen et al. 2000; Wagle et al. 2004). Data from the Demographic and Health Study (DHS), which was conducted in 40 countries between 1995 and 2003, show that more than half of infant mortality occurs after home births without the presence of experienced midwives (Lawn et al. 2005). In rural locations, Walraven et al. (1995) found that home deliveries without trained attendants resulted in perinatal mortality that was three times higher than that of births in a health facility with trained attendants.

Moreover, in Papua New Guinea, deliveries at home during apparently normal pregnancies were associated with a high prevalence of obstetric problems, according to Ganer et al. (1994). The government of

Tanzania encourages all expectant mothers to give birth at health facilities, and the country has a well-established network of medical facilities (Mosha et al. 2005). Also, the government has decreed that all government facilities must waive fees for deliveries and other mother and child health services (Ministry of Health, MOH, 2005). Yet, in practice, women are required to bring delivery kits, which typically include cotton wool, gloves, and razor blades.

National Bureau of Statistics & Macro International Inc. 2005; & Lugina et al. 2004) show that the majority of mothers in Tanzania and elsewhere attend antenatal clinics at least once during pregnancy, but that only a small percentage of them deliver in health facilities. Research has long focused on the location of delivery and the factors that influence it (Campbell & MacFarlane, 1986; Hodgkin, 1996; Campbell et al., 2006). The location of delivery is influenced by

socioeconomic factors and the distance to a medical facility (Yanagisawa et al. 2006). For instance, 84% of rural Tanzanian women who gave birth at home intended to do it at a health facility but were unable to do so due to issues with distance and transportation (Bicego et al. 1995).

Ghana observed a reduction in skilled delivery rate from 57 percent in 2014 to 56.5 percent in 2017 (Ghana Health Service, 2017). This had a ripple effect on the mortality rate in the country. The skilled delivery rate in deprived regions in Ghana still lags at a rate of 26.7%. The home delivery rate in the country as of 2017 stands at 20.0%, with rural regions having the highest proportion (UNICEF, 2017). Several maternal and child mortalities, as well as birth complications, could be avoided or managed successfully if pregnant women had access to a qualified birth attendant such as a doctor, nurse, or midwife during delivery

(Rawe, 2011). Previous studies show that the utilization of facility-based delivery is usually affected by sociocultural norms and several other factors including cost, long-distance, accessibility, availability, and quality of the services (Yaya et al., 2018). Women of low socioeconomic status have no money for transportation during labor and this compels them to deliver at home (Egharevba, et al., 2017).

These studies highlight the significance of socioeconomic considerations (among other things) in determining the place of birth; nevertheless, there is little literature that considers the experiences of mothers in accessing the free maternal healthcare policy. Even though ample studies have been conducted on health facilities deliveries, in the Ashanti Region of Ghana, there are no published studies conducted on home and facility deliveries in the Bekwai Municipality. This study therefore seeks to

bridge that gap in existing literature on the topic.

1.3 Research Objectives

1. To identify the determinants of home and facility deliveries
2. To find out the effects of a free maternal health policy on home deliveries
3. To explore the experiences of mothers in accessing free maternal health policy

1.4 Justification and Significance of the Study

This research aims to uncover the determinants of home and facility deliveries, as well as to identify the factors that influence the choice of home birth and to assess the accessibility of healthcare facilities. Additionally, it seeks to explore the effects of the free maternal health policy on home deliveries and to examine the experiences of

mothers in accessing the policy. For experts and researchers, this study provides a field-tested, evidence-based perspective on the issue of planned home birth and its corresponding challenges in Ghana, which can strengthen the policy framework. This study is crucial for several reasons. Firstly, it provides an in-depth understanding of how the free maternal healthcare policy has impacted home births. Secondly, it raises awareness among pregnant women and other women about maternal health issues and the importance of seeking proper care, as neglecting these issues can negatively affect their health and well-being. Lastly, it highlights the available interventions for home births and can inform future policies and interventions in this area.

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Home Birth

Homebirth is a natural childbirth that takes place in the home rather than a hospital or

birth center and is frequently attended by a midwife or lay attendant with experience in managing it (Farlex 2018). It can be attended or unattended. Before the development of modern medicine, giving birth at home was the standard procedure. As hospital births became more common in the middle of the 19th century, the phrase “home birth” was developed. Home delivery is still a significant issue in developing nations. Each year, approximately 303,000 women worldwide pass away from pregnancy-related causes and 99% of these deaths take place in developing nations. Home births can be either planned or unplanned and can be attended or unattended. When a trained professional, usually a midwife and occasionally a general practitioner, assists a woman during labor and delivery, it is referred to as an attended home birth. On the other hand, free birth occurs when a mother has no professional assistance or relies only

on the aid of a layperson, such as a doula, a partner, a family member, or a friend. A deliberate decision to give birth at home is known as a planned home birth.

2.1.2 The Healthcare System

Because maternal health care depends on a nation's overall health system, its results, including health-seeking behavior, can be linked to how health systems function (Parkhurst et al., 2005). The organization of maternal healthcare, which focuses on the availability of both private and public sectors, human resources, and reforms in the health sector is all included in the health system (Graham, 2002).

First of all, the presence of a trained birth attendant during delivery is widely seen as a human resource in maternal health services (Parkhurst et al., 2005; Hoop-Bender et al., 2006). This can be a doctor, a midwife, a nurse, or one of the traditional birth attendants (TBA) who are becoming more

prevalent but may not have received any midwifery training (WHO, 2004). The outcomes for maternal health are influenced by how easily these trained delivery attendants are accessible. However, studies have shown that the presence of these birth attendants may be ineffective if they are not properly coordinated so that they are accessible and have the resources necessary to carry out their duties should complications or, in the worst-case scenario, deaths occur (Graham et al., 2001; WHO, 2004; Parkhurst et al., 2005).

Second, the delivery of maternal health services and maternal health outcomes are influenced by both private and public health services (Parkhurst et al., 2005). Therefore, depending on their income and willingness to pay, people often choose between using private or public healthcare facilities for their medical needs. The ability and desire of individuals to pay for healthcare services,

however, is dependent on their earnings. Income disparities frequently result in disparities and inequalities in health-seeking behavior, which in turn affects the results for maternal health (Oppong et al., 1994; Agyepong, 1999). In developing and transitioning countries, like Ghana, the differences are greater (WHO, 2005). We can contend that the provision of high-quality healthcare can be established if income influences the facility where women seek medical attention. This is a result of the claim that private healthcare institutions tend to provide higher-quality services than public healthcare facilities (Wilson et al., 1997; Graham et al., 2001; Parkhurst et al., 2005).

Thirdly, there are healthcare reforms taking place on a worldwide scale. Decentralization of health services and the sector-wide approach (SWAp) are two important reforms, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa (Peter et al., 1998; Mayhew, 2003). Examples of

decentralized public administrations with clear roles at the national, regional, and district levels may be found in Ghana. The central administrations continue to play a more significant role, though (GOG, 1996; Mayhew, 2003). Regional hospitals and district health management teams have the status of Budget Management Centers, although the Ministry of Health (MOH) retains the policy-making responsibilities (GOG, 1996; Agyepong, 1999; Mayhew, 2003).

2.1.3 Ghana's National Health Insurance Scheme (NHIS)

Health insurance is a sort of insurance protection that pays for a covered person's hospital and surgery costs. Depending on the kind of health insurance, either the insured pays out-of-pocket and is then repaid, or the insurer pays the provider directly. The term "provider" in the context of health insurance refers to a clinic, hospital, physician,

laboratory, healthcare professional, or pharmacy. The person who owns the health insurance policy, or the "insured," is the one who has health insurance coverage (Nordqvist 2012).

The Ghanaian government implemented the NHIS in 2003 through the National Health Insurance Act of 2003. It aims to replace Ghanaians' reliance on the cash-and-carry system by giving them access to affordable healthcare (National Health Insurance Framework, 2004). To "secure the implementation of a national health insurance policy that ensures access to essential health care services for all residents," the NHIS was established (Blanchet, Fink & Osei-Akoto, 2012). The government's ultimate goal in establishing the NHIS was to offer an acceptable package of high-quality essential health services without requiring patients to pay out of pocket (National Health Insurance Framework, 2004).

2.1.4 Ghana`s Free Maternal Healthcare Program

A regulation that excused women from paying delivery costs in public, private, and mission facilities in Ghana was implemented by the Ghanaian government in 2008. Beginning with Ghana's four poorest regions, the northern, upper east, upper west, and central regions, it expanded to other areas of the nation in April 2005 (Witter, Adjei, Armar-Klemesu, & Graham, 2009). The goal of the strategy was to remove any obstacles that the NHIS policy would present for women. Reducing maternal mortality and improving women's health generally are the goals of the free maternal health care policy. It aims to lower the number of women and children who pass away from avoidable pregnancy and labor-related issues, encourages women to obtain ANC and PNC, and decrease the number of deliveries that take place outside of medical institutions

(Ghana Health Nest, 2012). A woman must be pregnant and have registered for the NHIS to be eligible for free maternal coverage. After a woman's pregnancy is confirmed, she is eligible for free maternal healthcare services until nine months after giving birth, and all of her children are covered until they are 90 days old (Ghana Health Nest, 2012).

The goal of the free maternal healthcare policy is to persuade women to give birth in hospitals. After the introduction of the free maternal health care policy, according to research by Bosu et al., there was an increase in facility deliveries (Bosu, Jacqueline, Armar-Klemesu, & Tornui, 2007). Data from the maternal ward, outpatient department, theater, emergency room, isolation ward, critical care unit, and mortuary in 9 hospitals in the Central region and 12 hospitals in the Volta region were used by Bosu et al. in 2007 to evaluate the free maternal health care policy.

Maternal mortality decreased as a result of the strategy, falling from 445 to 381 per 100,000 live births in the Central Region to 648 to 391 per 100,000 live births in the Volta Region. The two regions' changes weren't statistically different (Bosu, Jacqueline, Armar-Klemesu, & Tornui, 2007). Although the results of this study cannot be applied to the entire country of Ghana, they do provide a good indication of the effectiveness of the free maternal health care program in lowering maternal mortality. The insignificant result could be because the research used fewer data points for the analysis. The research used only one year before and after the policy to conduct the research.

2.2 Theoretical Foundation

2.2.1 Health Service Utilization Model

Ronald M. Andersen introduced the healthcare usage model in 1968 in the United States of America. He studied medical

sociology and health services. He created the model using data from a study on families' use of healthcare services conducted by the Center for Health Administration Studies and the National Opinion Research (Aday, Andersen, & Fleming, 1980; Hansen & Andersen, 2008). The hypothesis has undergone several changes since it was first developed.

Several disciplines, including sociology, medicine, public health, and psychology, have used the paradigm. The model is a multilevel hypothesis that includes determinants of the use of health services at the personal and contextual levels. In doing so, it divides the main contextual qualities into those that predispose to, facilitate, or suggest a need for individual use of health care, much like how individual characteristics have traditionally been divided (Anderson, 2008). The hypothesis is founded on three key ideas. These are

enabling, necessary, and predisposing factors. It explains how these factors interact to affect how often people use health services (Andersen, 2008). The following is an explanation of the model's key principles:

Predisposing factors

Predisposing factors, according to the Health Utilization Model, are people's demographic traits, which include sex and age as "biological imperatives" (Andersen & Davidson, 2001), social factors like religion, occupation, education, ethnicity, attitude toward health, and social relations (like family status), and mental factors like health beliefs. Values, attitudes, and knowledge about health and health-related services, for instance (Andersen, 1992; Andersen, 2008); and contextual factors, such as the social and demographic make-up of communities, organizational and collective values, political perspectives, and cultural norms, which

influence how likely people are to use health services.

Enabling factors

The approach describes enabling variables as being outside of the individual but significant in influencing his or her choices regarding the utilization of health services. Organizational and financial issues are thought to be prerequisites for using health services (Andersen & Davidson, 2001; Babitsch, Gohl, & von Lengerke, 2012). Both at the individual and contextual levels, these organizational and financial elements are present. Individual financing considerations include an individual's wealth and income that allow them to pay for the use of healthcare services as well as the actual cost of care, which is determined by cost-sharing obligations and their level of health insurance (Andersen, 2008). Access to a consistent source of care and the characteristics of that provider are individual organizational

factors. These also consist of waiting times for medical attention, travel time to the medical institution, and the mode of transportation (Andersen & Davidson, 2001; Babitsch, et al., 2012).

According to the model, financing at the contextual level includes the resources available within the environment for health services, such as wealth, per capita community income, the extent of health insurance coverage, methods of compensating providers, the relative cost of goods and services, and health care expenditures (Babitsch et al., 2012). The quantity, locations, types, structures, and distribution of health staff and facilities are all examples of organization at the contextual level. Additionally, it involves provider diversity, office hours, hospital and physician density, quality management monitoring, and outreach and education initiatives. Moreover, health policies are organizational contextual

enabling variables (Andersen & Davidson, 2001; Babitsch et al., 2012).

The Need Factors

The model's need factors, which are views of how serious a sickness or health condition is (Andersen & Newman, 1973; Babitsch et al., 2012), exist at both the individual and contextual levels, just as the enabling factors. The model makes a distinction between evaluated need (objective measurements of patients' health status and professional assessments, as well as the need for medical care) and perceived need (how people perceive and experience their health status (self-rated health), functional state, and illness symptoms) at the individual level (Andersen & Davidson, 2001; Babitsch et al., 2012).

Individuals distinguish between environmental need factors and population health indices at the contextual level (Babitsch et al., 2012). According to the

paradigm, environmental need refers to environmental conditions that have an impact on health (e.g., occupational and traffic and crime-related injury and death rates). On the other hand, population health indices are broad assessments of a community's health, encompassing epidemiological markers of mortality, illness, and disability (Andersen & Newman, 1973; Babitsch et al., 2012). The approach has drawn criticism for neglecting to take into account cultural aspects and social interactions (Wilson et al., 2005). However, Andersen (2008) contends that the predisposing feature components also include social structure (Anderson, 2008). Another critique was the concentration on need at the expense of social structures and health ideas (Wilson et al., 2005). However, according to Andersen (2008), need is a

social construct. Due to this, needs are divided into perceived and evaluated needs.

The model's emphasis on healthcare consumption or adoption of health outcomes as a binary factor—present or absent—is another drawback, according to Davidson (2001). Some models of help-seeking also take the kind of assistance source, such as unofficial sources, into account (Davidson, 2001). By adding online and other non-face-to-face sources, more recent research has advanced and more realistically examined help-seeking behaviors (Davidson, 2001). Despite the few flaws of the model, it has the following strengths; the model considers healthcare utilization from both the micro (individual) and the macro level (community) level. Predisposing factors clearly explain treatment selection. It includes material, environmental, and structural factors.

2.3 Conceptual Framework

Figure 1.0: Conceptual framework

Source: Field data, 2023

Figure 1.0 represents the conceptual framework for the study. In the diagram above, long distances from birth facilities, cost of healthcare, and availability of functional clinics are considered as the determinants of home and facility birth. These factors determine if one decides to choose home delivery or facility delivery.

3.1 Methodology

The overall strategy for the investigation is described in this section. It examines the best research methodology for analyzing the topic

under investigation. The methodology enables a rigorous assessment of the research's overall validity and dependability. It includes the study area, research design, population, sample size, sampling procedure, data collection and analysis, and ethical considerations.

3.1.1 Study Area

The Bekwai Municipal is located in the southern part of Ashanti Region. It shares boundaries with Bosomtwe District in the north, Adansi–North in the south, Bosome-

Freho District to the East and Amansie-Central and Amansie-West to the west. The Municipal Assembly lies within latitude 6° 00'N 6° 03 'N and Longitudes 1°00 W and 1° 35W. It covers a total land area of about 553.3sqkm representing 2.2 percent of the total land area of the region. The Bekwai Municipal Assembly is among the 43 Metropolitan, Municipal and District Assemblies in the Ashanti Region. The Municipal Assembly is the highest political and administrative body of the Municipal and exercises deliberative, legislative and executive functions. The Municipality was established under Legislative Instrument (L.I. 1906, 2007).

Politically and administratively, the Municipality covers the entire Bekwai Constituency. Some of the major settlements are Bekwai, Anwiankwanta, Dominase, Kokofu, Essumeja, Poano, Ofoase-Kokoben, Abodom, Bogyawe, Senfi, Huntado,

Amoaful, Dadease, Kensere, Akyeremade, Dotom, Koniyaw and Kokotro. The Bekwai Municipality has 36 electoral areas and has 8 Zonal Councils namely Bekwai, Essumeja, Dadease, Asuo-Dankran, Adagya, Adumasa, Kokofu and Adudwan. The population of the Municipality is 137,967 with 66,616 males and 71,351 females representing 48.3 percent and 51.7 percent respectively. The population in the age group 0-14 years makes up 48,084 representing 34.9%, while those between the ages 15-64 years constitute 82,101 representing 59.3%. Those who are 65+ years and above are 7,782 representing 15.8%.

The major healthcare services provider in the area is the Ashanti Bekwai Municipal Hospital. The hospital was established during the colonial period as a clinic for the staff of a colonial bank which was situated in a story building opposite the Clinic in Bekwai. The Clinic was later extended to cater for the inhabitants of Bekwai and its environs. The

facilities of the clinic were improved to meet the standards of a hospital. During the 1970's, the hospital was upgraded into a District Hospital that also served as a referral point to health facilities in and around the Amansie East District. In 2008, the Amansie East District attained a Municipality status and the hospital was subsequently upgraded into a Municipal Hospital.

The Bekwai Township where the hospital is located shares boundaries to the North with Dominase, East with Kokofu and Kortwia on the South. The hospital has about 16 units that render various kinds of services to the public in and around the municipality. The Units are Administration, Accounts, Records, Stores, Pharmacy, Surgical Ward, Theatre/Anesthesia, Laboratory, Maternity/Obstetrics and Gynecology, ENT/Dental, OPD, X-Ray, Psychiatric/Diabetic/Sickle Cell, Accident and Emergency, Public health, General

Wards (Pediatrics, Children, Female and Male). The kinds of services the hospital provides include the following; OPD services, Consultation, In-Patient services, Obstetric and Gynecological services, Accident and Emergency services, Pharmaceutical services, ECG, Anti-Natal (ANC) and Pre-Natal Care (PNC) services, Anti-Retroviral Therapy (ART) and Counseling, Laboratory services, X-Ray services, Ultra Sound, Ear Nose Throat and Dental services (ENT), Community Psychiatric services, Reproductive and Child Health Care services (RCH), Maternal Health services, Diabetic and Sickle Cell services. The hospital also serves as a referral point to Kokofu hospital, health centres, clinics and other health facilities that fall outside the municipality (Bekwai Municipal Hospital, 2016).

3.1.2 Research Design

A systematic mixed-methods research approach was used in this study. According to Creswell (2014), a mixed methods research design involves combining or mixing both qualitative and quantitative research and data into a single study. Quantitative data originates from closed-ended data sources like tests, questionnaires, or psychological instruments, whereas qualitative data is acquired from open-ended sources that typically do not have predesigned responses (Creswell, 2014). A mixed-method research is the gathering, analysis, and integration of quantitative and qualitative data in a single or multiphase study (Hanson et al. 2005).

In more detailed words, Tashakkori and Creswell (2007) developed mixed-method research projects, concentrating on the requirement of manifestation of merging in each step. They define it as a study or program of inquiry in which the researcher

gathers and analyses data, integrates the results, and develops conclusions utilizing both qualitative and quantitative methodologies. In other words, high-quality mixed-methods research incorporates mixing at every level of the research process, including the formulation of the research questions, sampling, data collecting, analysis, and interpretation (Yin, 2006).

3.1.3 Sample Size

Since the study adopts a mixed methods research approach, different sample sizes were used for different purposes. Hence, the sample size for the qualitative research was different from that of the quantitative research approach. According to Crouch (2006), small samples of less than 20 increase the validity of fine-grained and in-depth inquiry in qualitative research, particularly for interview-based research. To ensure that there were samples, the researcher always tried to get more referrals in case some of the

people he approached declined to participate. For the qualitative study, a total of 15 participants were targeted. All fifteen (15) targeted participants were mothers who responded to interview questions on their experiences in accessing the free maternal healthcare policy.

In the quantitative study, 182 respondents (mothers) responded to a self-administered questionnaire constructed by the researcher. The self-administered questionnaire was targeted at identifying the determinants of home and facility deliveries, and to also find out the effects of free maternal healthcare policy on home deliveries. Despite being restricted to a population that can read and write, the questionnaire was deemed adequate for the study because it is less expensive and time-consuming. There was also the advantage of guaranteeing privacy because there is no face-to-face interaction, unlike during an interview (Sharma, 2017).

3.1.4 Sampling Procedure

The respondents were chosen through purposeful sampling. According to Bryman (2004), a practice known as "purposive sampling" involves selecting respondents depending on how well they relate to the subject of the study. According to Creswell and Plano-Clark (2007), purposeful sampling enables the researcher to pick precisely those people who have firsthand experience of the important phenomenon or the central concept under inquiry. Sarantakos (1998), which was quoted by Amedahe (2002), backs up this claim concerning the purposive sampling technique. Amedahe (2002) added that while using the purposive sample technique, researchers deliberately select respondents who, in their opinion, are presumed to be pertinent to the research topic and objectives. The logic and efficacy of purposeful sampling, according to Patton (2002), lie in selecting cases that provide a plethora of data

for in-depth examination. To gather the necessary data, the researchers were able to sample viewpoints from various groups of people. People who were regarded to be knowledgeable about the topic at hand were available for the researchers to choose from. Second, the instrument design was appropriate given the study's research objectives. The questionnaire also accurately depicts the subject of the study, was appropriate for the target demographic, measured the variables it was intended to evaluate, and was extensive enough to collect all the information needed to solve the issues of the study.

3.1.5 Data Collection Instruments

A custom questionnaire was used to survey the respondents, and interview scripts were used to conduct the interviews. A questionnaire is a research tool that is employed in surveys to collect self-reported responses for both general and targeted issues

(Gravetter & Forzano, 2009). The questionnaire is deemed adequate for the study even though it is limited to a group that can read and write because it is less expensive and time-consuming. Because there is no face-to-face connection, unlike during an interview, anonymity is also assured (Kumar, 1999). The determinants of home and facility deliveries and the effects of free maternal healthcare policy on home deliveries were investigated using a questionnaire. Several selected mothers within study region were given these questionnaires. Participants who could not read and understand the questionnaire were guided by the researcher.

The qualitative research approach was utilized to collect information by conducting open-ended interviews with a few chosen mothers on their experiences with the free maternity healthcare policy. According to Dilshad and Latif (2013), the main goal of research interviews is to gather pertinent data

from the respondents that will be utilized to describe, forecast, and explain a phenomenon based on emotions, sentiments, and experiences. In-depth interviews were used in this study, based on Guion and Diehl's (2013) claim that qualitative interviews are effective instruments to employ in planning and assessing programs since they use an open-ended, discovery-oriented strategy.

To make sure that the questionnaire and interview guide have relevant items that could answer the research questions and objectives, the instruments were organized into sections, with each segment focusing on one of the study's objectives. However, the first component provides information about the participants' demographics. The primary demographic characteristics were age, marital status, occupation, and educational background. These demographics were crucial for assessing how they related to the

objectives and research questions of the study.

3.1.7 Data Analysis Techniques

The researcher's use of coding for qualitative analysis is beneficial when investigating insider perspectives on the research question (Padgett, 2008). After each interview was complete, the researcher precisely translated the audio file using Microsoft Word; a separate Word document for each transcript included demographic data and an Interviewee 1–15 coding scheme. After coding, categorizing, and theming the data, the researcher went over each interview in turn and highlighted direct quotes and words that were significant and influential to the study subject. The quotes were then assigned as Nvivo quotes, or verbatim statements, to one of the study's three (3) themes (Saldaa, 2013). In Microsoft Word, the researcher underlined and noted which theme each passage related to.

The IBM Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) computer program was used to prepare, code, and enter quantitative data. The researcher used percentages, and tables to analyze the quantitative data that was gathered from the respondents. The effects of the free maternal healthcare policy on home deliveries were also examined.

3.1.8 Ethical Considerations

As part of the informed consent process, participants were provided with a permission letter describing the study's objectives, their involvement in the investigation, and the measures taken to protect and disclose their information. The informed consent process also informed participants that they had the option to opt out of the study and were free to leave at any time while the data was being collected. The study's goals, justifications, and benefits of participating were then explained to the participants to ensure that they were fully informed before deciding to

participate. The researcher kept participant identification on file until all data was collected. Additionally, all publications and presentations only used cumulative statistics, and all personally identifiable information was kept anonymous. The principle of voluntarism was also followed, where participants were free to decide whether or not to participate in the study without any pressure or coercion. To maintain anonymity during the trial, any identifying information, including the name of the participant, was hidden using pseudonyms.

PRESENTATION OF THE DATA

4.1 Presentation of Quantitative Data

The chapter provides the results of the study, condensing the information into an understandable account that highlights the study's many features. The presentation starts by carefully analyzing the quantitative data, where statistical percentages and figures provide quantitative insights into the

prevalence and patterns of home deliveries since the policy's implementation. After that, the chapter proceeds to the qualitative

component, where participant accounts, viewpoints, and experiences are further highlighted.

4.1.1 Socio-demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age		
Under 18 years	9	4.9
18-24 years	21	11.5
25-34 years	34	18.7
35-44 years	44	24.2
45-54 years	39	21.4
55 years or above	33	18.1
Missing	2	1.1
Religious affiliation		
Christian	138	75.8
Muslim	38	20.9
Traditional	5	2.7
Any other	1	0.6
Level of Education		
Never schooled	23	12.6
Elementary	14	7.7
JSS/JHSS	56	30.8
O`level / A`level	4	2.2
SSSCE/ WASSCE	43	23.6
Diploma / HND	8	4.4
Graduate	31	17.0
Post-Graduate	2	1.1
Occupation		
Employed (full-time)	56	30.8
Employed (part-time)	9	4.9
Self-employed	81	44.5
Unemployed	25	13.7
Student	10	5.5
Other (Specify)	1	.5

Marital Status		
Single	40	22.0
Separated	18	9.9
Divorced	11	6.0
Married	91	50.0
Widowed	21	11.5

Source: Field data, 2023

The age group of 35-44 years emerged as the one with the highest prevalence, accounting for the majority of the sample (24.2%). The 25-34 years group followed closely, constituting 18.7% of the participants, while the 45-54 years group came in third with 21.4%. These age groups played a significant role in the study. The 18-24 years and 55 years or above groups made up 11.5% and 18.1%, respectively, while the smallest representation belonged to the Under 18 years category, at 4.9%. It is worth noting that there are 2 missing data points, accounting for 1.1% of the total, which may require further investigation or imputation.

Christianity proved to be the most prevalent religion among the participants, making up

75.8% of the sample, with 138 individuals.

The Muslim faith came in second, accounting for 20.9% of the sample, with 38 people.

Traditional beliefs were represented by a much smaller proportion, with only 5 individuals making up 2.7% of the sample.

Moreover, the number of participants identifying with "Any other" religion was extremely low, constituting only 0.6% of the sample and comprising only one person.

According to the data, there is a diverse range of educational backgrounds among the individuals in the sample. The largest group, comprising 56 people and making up 30.8% of the sample, have completed junior secondary school (JSS) or junior high school (JHSS). Following closely behind are those

who have completed the Senior Secondary School Certificate Examination (SSSCE) or the West African Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE), accounting for 23.6% of participants and 43 people. The study also includes graduates, with 31 people at 17%, and those with a Diploma or Higher National Diploma (HND), with 8 people at 4.4%. People with O'level or A'level schooling make up 2.2% of the sample, while people without any formal education make up 12.6% of the participants. Post-Graduate education has the lowest representation in the sample with only 2 people or 1.1% of the total.

The largest group in the sample is comprised of self-employed individuals, accounting for 44.5% with 81 people. Full-time workers come in second with 30.8%, represented by 56 individuals. A smaller yet still significant

group of 25 people, or 13.7%, are unemployed. Part-time workers make up 4.9% of the population, consisting of 9 individuals, while students represent 5.5% with 10 individuals. Only 1 person, or 0.5% of the total population, falls into the "Other (Specify)" category.

In terms of marital status, the data shows that married individuals make up the largest group, representing 50.0% of the 91 participants. The "Single" group comes in second with 22.0%, consisting of 40 individuals. Additionally, some participants identify as "Widowed," representing 21 people or 11.5% of the sample. People who are "separated" make up 9.9% of participants with 18 individuals, while those who are "divorced" account for 6.0% with 11 individuals.

4.1.2 Determinants of Planned Home or Facility Birth

Table 2: Determinants of Planned Home or Facility Birth

Determinants	Frequency	Percentage
Facility delivery		
Yes	179	98.4
No	3	1.6
Safer Option		
Home delivery	8	4.4
Facility delivery	167	91.8
Not sure	7	3.8
Choice of place of delivery		
Yes, home delivery	29	15.9
Yes, facility delivery	136	74.7
No, neither	17	9.3
Factors of home birth		
Cost	20	11.0
Cultural beliefs and practices	7	3.8
Difficulty in accessing healthcare facilities	6	3.3
Trust in traditional birth attendants	7	3.8
Lack of trust in healthcare facilities	5	2.7
Privacy and comfort	6	3.3
Not applicable (I would choose facility delivery)	131	72.0
Factors of facility delivery		
Access to skilled healthcare professionals	30	16.5
Safety and emergency care availability	23	12.6
Availability of medical equipment and supplies	19	10.4
Trust in healthcare facilities	27	14.8
Previous negative experiences with home deliveries	14	7.7
Insurance coverage	18	9.9
Not applicable (I would choose home delivery)	51	28.0

Source: Field data, 2023.

According to the data presented in Table 2, 98.4% or 179 women, chose facility delivery the overwhelming majority of the sample, over home delivery. Only 1.6%, or 3 women,

opted for home delivery. Interestingly, 4.4% of the sample, or 8 people, reported giving birth at home. The majority of participants, 91.8% or 167 people, selected facility delivery, indicating that they gave birth in a medical facility. Only 7.2% of respondents were unsure of their delivery location.

It is clear that the majority of women surveyed, 74.7%, chose to give birth in a medical facility, highlighting the importance of hospitals, clinics, and polyclinics for maternal health. 15.9% of participants opted for a home birth, indicating a slightly lower but still significant percentage who favored it. It is noteworthy that cost was a key consideration for approximately 11.0% of women, indicating the importance of financial concerns in this decision.

Interestingly, 72.0% of respondents said they would choose hospital delivery, indicating a clear preference for giving birth in a hospital. Nearly 16.5% of participants identified access to qualified healthcare professionals as a crucial element. Safety and emergency care accessibility were cited by 12.6% of respondents as significant, while 10.4% of women mentioned the availability of medical supplies and equipment.

Trust in medical institutions was important to 14.8% of women. About 7.7% of mothers said that their preference for facility delivery was motivated by prior bad experiences with home deliveries. 9.9% of individuals mentioned insurance, indicating that having healthcare coverage affected their decision.

4.1.3 Effects of the Free Maternal Healthcare Policy on Home Deliveries

Table 3: Effects of the Free Maternal Healthcare Policy on Decision Regarding Home Deliveries

Effects	Frequency	Percentage
1. Influence of the Free Maternal Health policy on home delivery		
Yes, positively influenced my decision	35	19.2

Yes, negatively influenced my decision	9	4.9
No, it did not influence my decision	65	35.7
Not applicable (I did not consider home delivery)	70	38.5
Missing	3	1.65
2. Changes in the prevalence of home deliveries		
Yes, there has been a decrease in home deliveries	119	65.4
Yes, there has been an increase in home deliveries	2	1.0
No, there has been no noticeable change	26	14.3
Not applicable (I have no information or experience regarding this)	35	19.2

Source: Field data, 2023.

Mothers were asked to share how the Free Maternal Health program impacted their decision-making around home deliveries. Results showed that 19.2% of women were inspired by the program to consider a home birth, while 4.9% felt dissuaded from this choice. A significant number of respondents (35.7%) reported that the program had no impact on their decision, while 38.5% indicated that they had never considered

home delivery as an option. It is worth noting that 3 women did not respond to this question, accounting for 1.65% of the total. In terms of overall trends, 65.4% of mothers reported a decrease in home births since the program's implementation, while only 1.0% noted an increase. Interestingly, 14.3% of participants did not observe a noticeable shift in-home delivery rate.

4.1.4 Main Advantages of Delivering in a Healthcare Facility

Table 4: Main Advantages of Delivering in a Healthcare Facility

Advantages	Frequency	Percentage
Access to skilled healthcare professionals	52	28.6
Availability of necessary medical equipment and supplies	40	22.0
Improved safety and emergency care	20	11.0
Availability of specialized care for potential complications	25	13.7
Lower risk of infections or complications	27	14.9

Not applicable (I prefer home delivery)
Source: Field data, 2023.

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9.9

According to the table, almost 28.6% of respondents highlighted the value of having access to qualified healthcare professionals. Second, 22.0% of respondents identified the availability of essential medical supplies and equipment as a major benefit, highlighting the significance of having the appropriate resources on hand during labor. How Based on the data presented, it appears that a significant portion of respondents, nearly 28.6%, emphasized the importance of having

access to skilled healthcare professionals. Additionally, 22.0% of participants recognized the value of having essential medical supplies and equipment readily available during childbirth. However, a small percentage of respondents, only 9.9%, indicated a preference for home delivery, suggesting that some individuals may not prioritize the benefits of facility deliveries in their decision-making process.

4.2 Presentation of Qualitative Data

4.2.1 Determinants of Planned Home or Facility Birth

The choice of place to give birth, whether at home or in a hospital, clinic, or polyclinic, is an important aspect of maternal healthcare and has a significant impact on the results for both the mother and the newborn. In the context of Ghana, where the Free Maternal Healthcare Policy has been established to

expand access to maternal healthcare services, understanding the variables influencing this choice is essential. The study examined the responses from various participants as they discussed their thoughts on all the factors affecting the location of their delivery in this situation.

“I will always choose hospital over delivering a bay at home. The hospital is always safer, especially in situations of emergencies.” (Participant 2)

“I have three children, the first one is currently at the university, and he was the only one gave birth to at home. But for the last two, I made sure I went to the hospital. So, for the facility delivery, it is always good” (Participant 5)

“In this modern world, everybody will choose facility delivery over home delivery. If you give birth at home and there are complications, even your community members will scold you. They will ask if you are the correct being.” (Participant 8)

“[Oh] I am an old woman. I gave birth to all my children at home. I did not face any complications, but then that was long ago. But, of course, I know that facility delivery is good.”

“Either home or facility delivery, it is all good. But then the facility delivery is much safer.” (Participant 15)

4.2.2 Effects of the Free Maternal Health

Policy on Home Deliveries

4.2.2.1 Improved Safety and Emergency Response

The analysis of the participant's experiences in the Free Maternal Health Policy revealed a

significant and recurring issue related to increased safety and emergency response during home deliveries. This crucial aspect emphasizes the policy's impact on ensuring the safety and well-being of new mothers and their babies during childbirth. The policy, designed to eliminate financial barriers to maternal healthcare services in Ghana, has had a substantial influence on the safety practices surrounding childbirth, as indicated by the participants' views. They highlighted how the policy has enhanced the security of maternal healthcare, particularly by enabling faster access to skilled medical professionals and emergency care in case of complications.

“I went through cesarean surgery twice. The baby did not turn well during the first pregnancy. The second time they had to cut open my cervix because it was too small to allow the baby to come out. I had my second baby like a month ago, and the wound has not healed yet.” (Participant 13)

“Since the introduction of the Free Maternal Health Policy, I've noticed a significant improvement in safety during childbirth. In the past, home

deliveries could be quite risky, especially if complications arose. But now, with access to healthcare facilities, I feel much safer knowing that skilled professionals and emergency care are available to handle any unexpected situations." (Participant 4)

"When my daughter was expecting, we decided to go to the nearby health center instead of opting for a home delivery. The healthcare staff were well-prepared for any emergencies, and it gave us peace of mind knowing that help was just a call away." (Participant 11)

"The most notable change is the enhanced safety during childbirth. Before, home deliveries were common, and we had limited access to emergency care. Now, with the Bekwai hospital nearby, we can rely on trained professionals and feel more secure about the well-being of both the mother and the baby." (Participant 1)

4.2.2.2 Increased Accessibility to Prenatal and Maternal Care

Participants highlighted their personal experiences and opinions regarding how the Free Maternal Health Policy has significantly improved access to prenatal and maternal care at medical facilities created specifically to meet the special requirements of pregnant

moms. In addition to providing thorough prenatal care, these facilities also offer secure, well-equipped birthing rooms.

"More healthcare centers are offering maternal care services now. There are hospitals and clinics all over. As soon as you experience a little bit of discomfort, you are likely to go to the hospital nearby. They will then check you and tell you what the issue is, and you will know what next to do." (Participant 11)

"When I was pregnant, I used to go to the hospital every month for check-ups, just to see how the baby was doing. The doctors will then make some recommendations and prescriptions. These helped me and the baby a lot." (Participant 14)

"Access to prenatal and birthing facilities has improved greatly. We now have well-equipped clinics and hospitals nearby that offer prenatal check-ups and support throughout pregnancy. This was a major factor in my decision to opt for facility delivery." (Participant 8)

4.2.2.3 Increased Access to Quality Healthcare

The words of one participant highlight how the Free Maternal Health Policy has increased pregnant women's access to high-quality medical care. According to the

interviews, previously many women had trouble getting to hospitals because they were often spread out and challenging to get to, especially in an emergency.

"The policy has undoubtedly increased access to quality healthcare. In the past, we had to travel long distances to get to a hospital, which was not always feasible. Now, with healthcare centers closer to us, we can access quality care, making it easier to choose facility delivery."
(Participant 5)

However, after the policy's implementation, it has grown simpler to access local healthcare facilities. Because of the proximity of healthcare facilities, pregnant women now have better access to high-quality care, which has also encouraged them to select facility birth because they know that qualified staff and the resources they need are nearby.

4.2.2.4 Financial Relief and Decision Making

The study's results provided insight into how the free maternal healthcare policy affected mothers' healthcare decision-making processes. The participants held a favorable view of the policy, maintaining that those who deny its worth are not well informed. The primary justification for the perceived advantage of the policy was its capacity to alleviate the financial strain associated with medical care.

"I would consider anyone a liar when he or she thinks this policy (free maternal healthcare policy) is of no use. Because the policy has made it possible for us to receive medical attention without too much financial burdens. It is not entirely free of charge these days, but it reduces a section of our financial burden. This was a decisive factor for me in choosing facility delivery."(Participant 2)

The recognition that the policy is not completely free indicates that there could be some additional expenses, but the individual highlights the substantial decrease in financial responsibility. This reduction in financial constraints is viewed as a crucial

element that has swayed the individual's decision to opt for facility birth, which involves giving birth in a healthcare facility like a hospital or clinic, rather than at home.

4.2.2.5 Shift toward Skilled Professional Healthcare Professionals

Findings from the study highlight a significant shift in the healthcare landscape, specifically in the context of maternal and child care. Participants emphasize a departure from reliance solely on traditional birth attendants and traditional remedies, signaling a transition towards the involvement of skilled healthcare professionals in ensuring the well-being of mothers and infants.

The acknowledgment of the effectiveness of traditional remedies coexists with the recognition of the changing times and the advantages brought about by modern healthcare practices. The emphasis on skilled healthcare professionals suggests a growing

awareness of the benefits associated with receiving care from individuals with formal training and expertise in the field.

“We no longer have to rely solely on traditional birth attendants though our traditional remedies are also effective. We are modern times, and things have changed. Now, we have skilled healthcare professionals who provide comprehensive care, making it safer for mothers and babies.”

“The doctors are professionals, and are experienced in this field. So going to the hospital makes one safer.” (Participant 12)

The use of the term "comprehensive care" underscores the idea that skilled healthcare professionals are capable of providing a more thorough and integrated approach to healthcare, potentially encompassing preventive measures, diagnostics, and treatment. The shift towards seeking care in hospitals, as mentioned in the second quote, is presented as a safer option. This perception may be grounded in the belief that hospitals provide a controlled and medically equipped environment, where trained professionals can

address a range of health concerns with a higher degree of efficacy and safety.

4.2.2.5 Availability of Sophisticated Medical Tools and Equipment

One of the participants offered a statement that went into detail on the policy's real effects in ensuring that hospitals have the necessary sophisticated medical equipment for giving delivery. This emphasizes how important it is to have the appropriate tools on hand to handle any unexpected events that may arise during the delivery process.

"Have you not seen the kind of tools available at the hospital? They are sophisticated, especially X-rays and things like that. You will not have access to these things when you give birth at home. It is only in the hospital." (Participant 10)

A mother stated that before the policy, there were instances when healthcare facilities encountered shortages and lacked the essential items required for safe delivery, causing hazards to both mothers and newborns. The women

acknowledged that this sector has seen some improvement since the policy's implementation. Even if there may still be problems, the policy has contributed to an improvement by making it easier to obtain the equipment needed for safer and more effective maternity healthcare services.

"Before the policy, there were times when healthcare facilities lacked the basic equipment needed for safe deliveries. Now, there's a little bit of noticeable improvement in this aspect." (Participant 4)

4.2.2.6 Accessibility and Adequacy of Healthcare Facilities

"Now we have two major health centers and they are all well-equipped. They have built a new hospital at that side [pointing to the direction of the newly-built hospital] in addition to the old one there [pointing to the direction of the old hospital]. They are all not very far from here. Most of the drugs that are prescribed to us are sold right there in the hospital. And you are transferred when your issue is critical. Apart from that they handle almost every issue because they have the equipment." (Participant 14)

4.2.3 Experiences of Mothers with Regard to the Free Maternal Healthcare Policy

The researchers conducted an extensive study to examine the impact of the Free Maternal Health Policy on maternal healthcare in Ghana. This policy aimed to improve maternal and child health outcomes and has significantly changed delivery practices in the country. The study explores the critical question of whether the policy has led to a reduction in the number of home births and assesses its effectiveness in achieving its objectives. The researchers gathered the experiences and views of mothers to determine the extent to which the policy has altered the choices of Ghanaian women regarding maternity care.

“This is a modern world. Things have changed. Almost everybody is choosing the facility delivery. At the hospital, if you face certain complications, it is easier to determine what the complication is and suggest remedies like caesarian surgery.” (Participant 1)

“It is not true. These things are just in the papers. If you go to the hospital to deliver, you are likely to spend not less than GHC 1,000.” (Participant 7)

"I've lived in this community for more than twenty years, and I can say with confidence that there has been a noticeable decrease in home deliveries since the Free Maternal Health Policy came into effect. More women are opting for facility deliveries because they know it's accessible and affordable." (Participant 6)

"Oh yes, home deliveries have declined, somehow. Before the policy, it was quite common, but now, most women prefer to give birth in healthcare facilities. The Bekwai hospital is just here [pointing towards the direction of the hospital]. And we know we have a newly built Bekwai hospital too, in that direction." [Pointing towards the newly-built hospital]. Every pregnant woman in this community goes there for so it's a positive change that ensures safer deliveries. It helps" (Participant 5)

The Free Maternal Health Policy's impact on home deliveries created a divide among some women. While some participants reported a noticeable decrease in home births following the implementation of the policy, others insisted that they had not witnessed any

change. The differing opinions highlight the difficulty in evaluating the program's effectiveness and imply that its outcomes can differ based on the experiences of mothers across various Ghanaian communities and regions.

"From my perspective, there has not been a significant change in the prevalence of home deliveries. While some women have started choosing healthcare facilities, there are still a few who prefer home deliveries due to personal reasons. For example, I have a colleague who no longer delivers at the hospital because of the attitude of the hospital attendants and nurses and things like that. So, I would say..... I cannot just conclude on that yet" (Participant 9)

"[oh] I cannot boldly say the free maternal healthcare policy has resulted in changes in the prevalence of home deliveries because people are still giving birth at home. We still have people who use our local herbs and they are very effective." (Participant 7)

"I haven't noticed a substantial change in the number of home deliveries. Some women in our community are quite traditional and continue to opt for home births. The policy has made a difference, but it hasn't eliminated home deliveries." (Participant 3)

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

4.3 Discussion of Quantitative Results

This section goes into greater detail about the discussion of these findings and their larger implications for maternal health policy and practices in Ghana. The goal is to assess the study's consequences, place them in the context of existing research, and provide policymakers and healthcare professionals with recommendations. The chapter intends to add to the ongoing conversation on maternal healthcare in Ghana and provide guidance for upcoming initiatives aimed at enhancing maternal and child health outcomes.

4.3.1 Determinants of Planned Home or Facility Birth

4.3.1.1 Choice of Place of Delivery

The study revealed that nearly all women, 98.4%, preferred giving birth in a hospital, clinic, or polyclinic, indicating a clear

inclination toward facility deliveries. This preference can be attributed to the success of the Free Maternal Health Policy, which aims to promote facility deliveries. Only a small fraction of women, 1.6%, opted for home births. The study's findings are encouraging, as they suggest that the policy has effectively encouraged a significant number of expectant mothers to choose facility births, which bodes well for maternal and child health outcomes. However, the low percentage of women choosing home births highlights the need for continued efforts to promote facility births and ensure universal access to quality maternal healthcare services. The study emphasizes the critical role of healthcare infrastructure and accessibility in supporting facility deliveries, especially since the majority of participants had access to healthcare facilities.

4.3.1.2 Safer Option for Delivering a Baby

The study revealed that the vast majority of mothers, around 91.8%, showed a strong preference for hospital deliveries. This marks a significant shift towards seeking expert and qualified care during childbirth, which is crucial for the well-being of both the mother and the newborn. The low percentage of women, only 4.4%, opting for home deliveries suggests a reduced reliance on traditional home births due to the Free Maternal Health Policy. This may indicate a greater awareness of the advantages of facility-based deliveries, such as access to medical expertise and emergency treatment. However, the uncertainty surrounding delivery location, observed in 7.2% of women, including 3.8% of the overall sample, suggests that some women may still face reservations or barriers in making a definitive decision.

The Free Maternal Health Policy seems to have successfully encouraged expectant mothers in Ghana to seek out skilled healthcare services during childbirth, which can significantly improve maternal and neonatal outcomes. These findings indicate a positive trend towards facility-based childbirth and highlight the importance of eliminating any remaining doubts or obstacles so that all expectant mothers can make an informed decision about where to deliver their baby in a safe environment.

4.3.1.3 Experiences of Mothers with regard to Place of Delivery

The study has revealed that women in Ghana have a diverse range of preferences when it comes to giving birth. While the majority (74.7%) opt for hospital delivery, a significant percentage (15.9%) still prefer home delivery. This variation indicates that people's decisions are influenced by societal, logistical, or personal factors, and highlights

the importance of personalized maternal healthcare services that respect people's preferences. The predominance of facility births is a positive trend that emphasizes the value of hospitals and healthcare institutions in providing for pregnant women, as it ensures accessibility to essential medical supplies and qualified healthcare professionals. The presence of a group (9.3%) that chooses neither home nor medical facility delivery underscores the need for accessible and responsive maternity healthcare services that address cultural concerns. Healthcare professionals and policymakers must recognize and respect the diversity of birth preferences while prioritizing safety and well-being during labor.

4.3.1.4 Factors Influencing Decision to Choose Home Delivery over Facility Delivery

The fact that more than 11% of women cited cost as a significant factor in choosing a home delivery highlights the challenges many faces in affording maternal healthcare. This indicates that some expectant mothers in Ghana may avoid medical facilities due to concerns about the expenses associated with hospital deliveries, such as medical bills and transportation costs. It is crucial to implement initiatives that improve the affordability and accessibility of maternal healthcare services to address this problem. This may involve reducing healthcare costs, providing financial assistance, or strengthening health insurance programs. The 3.8% of women who mentioned cultural customs and attitudes as influencing their birthing decisions underscores the importance of cultural factors in determining childbirth choices. These women may follow traditional cultural norms or beliefs that support home births or other cultural practices related to childbirth.

Given the impact of culture, it is essential to develop maternal healthcare interventions that are culturally sensitive. To accomplish this, it is necessary to engage with local communities, respect cultural customs, and provide education in line with cultural norms while emphasizing the importance of safe and expert attendance during childbirth.

The fact that 3.3% of mothers faced challenges accessing healthcare services sheds light on the geographic barriers that hinder healthcare access for some people. These obstacles may arise from living in remote or underdeveloped areas with limited or faraway healthcare facilities. To tackle this issue, efforts should focus on improving healthcare accessibility, particularly in rural and distant regions. Ensuring that expectant mothers can easily access healthcare services during childbirth may involve enhancing healthcare infrastructure, setting up mobile clinics, or providing transportation options.

The discovery that 3.8% of women's decision-making was influenced by their trust in traditional birth attendants underscores the enduring value of traditional practices and their ability to instill confidence in traditional healthcare practitioners. Because of long-standing cultural traditions, some individuals may have a deep-rooted faith in customary birth attendants. Acknowledging the significance of traditional ways of doing things, healthcare initiatives should explore ways to integrate customary birth attendants while upholding safety and sanitation protocols. Collaborating with conventional and modern medical professionals may foster trust and improve maternal health outcomes.

The findings that 2.7% of mothers lacked confidence in medical facilities highlight the importance of addressing trust issues within the healthcare sector. Building trust with healthcare facilities is essential and can be achieved by engaging the community,

maintaining transparency about healthcare procedures, and striving to improve the quality of care delivered at medical facilities.

The healthcare system must work to restore its reputation to encourage hospital deliveries, as indicated by the fact that 3.3% of women had privacy and comfort concerns during childbirth.

The fact that the majority of women (72.0%) preferred hospital delivery suggests a general preference for receiving healthcare services at healthcare facilities. This preference provides an opportunity to enhance maternal healthcare services delivered in hospitals.

4.3.2 Effects of the Free Maternal Health Policy on Home Deliveries

4.3.2.1 Influence of Free Maternal Health on Decision Regarding Home Deliveries

The Free Maternal Health program has shown promising results in encouraging some expectant mothers to consider home

delivery as a viable option. 19.2% of women reported feeling inspired to choose this route, highlighting the potential for the program to expand the available options for maternal healthcare. However, the 4.9% of women who reported negative impacts on their decision-making process suggest that there may be specific elements of the program that discourage home deliveries. Addressing these concerns can help improve the program's performance. It is important to note that the complexity of factors influencing delivery decisions is evident in the fact that 35.7% of women were not influenced by the program. Additionally, 38.5% of mothers expressed a strong preference for hospital births and felt that the program was meaningless in their case. Finally, three women did not respond to the question, resulting in 1.65% of missing data points.

4.3.2.2 Experiences of Mothers with regards to the Free Maternal Healthcare Policy

The program has succeeded in reducing home births, with 65.4% reporting a decline. This shift towards medical settings may improve maternal health outcomes. However, a small proportion (1.0%) experienced an increase in home births, indicating the need for ongoing monitoring to address exceptions. The 14.3% who saw no change suggest that policy effects may vary by region or community, necessitating tailored actions. Finally, the 19.2% with no knowledge of changes underscore the importance of collecting comprehensive data and understanding the impact on consumers.

4.3.2.3 Main Advantages of Delivering in a Healthcare Facility

The significance of having qualified healthcare practitioners available during childbirth cannot be overstated, as

demonstrated by the emphasis on having access to them (28.6%). This underscores the importance of strengthening the healthcare workforce and ensuring adequate staffing in maternity healthcare institutions. Additionally, the acknowledgment by 22.0% of mothers regarding the accessibility of necessary medical supplies and equipment underscores the critical role that resources play in ensuring a healthy and successful delivery. Maternal health is reliant on access to facilities with modern medical technology. Healthcare institutions provide a secure atmosphere with improved emergency response capabilities, as evidenced by the acknowledgment of improved emergency treatment and safety (11.0%), highlighting the value of being prepared for unexpected delivery situations. The significance of specialist treatment (13.7%) emphasizes the role that healthcare facilities play in managing complicated difficulties associated

with childbirth. To meet the diverse demands of maternal health, tailored services are essential.

The importance of a hygienic and regulated setting during labor is highlighted by the emphasis on a clean and controlled environment (14.9%), which reduces the risk of infections or complications. The fact that some participants (9.9%) preferred home births illustrate the variety of delivery options. It is crucial to respect individual preferences while ensuring that those who choose facility deliveries have access to specialist maternal healthcare services.

DISCUSSION OF THE QUALITATIVE DATA

4.4 Determinants of Planned Home or Facility Birth

The viewpoints of the participants on where to give birth provide valuable insight regarding the variables impacting this crucial

choice in Ghana, particularly in light of the Free Maternal Healthcare Policy. Several mothers, according to the research, highlighted how safe it is to give birth at a hospital, clinic, or polyclinics. They believe hospitals, clinics, or polyclinics to be safer, especially during emergencies. This emphasizes how crucial it is to have access to emergency care resources and trained healthcare personnel, both of which are frequently more easily accessible at healthcare facilities (Yaya et al., 2021). Certain individuals open up about their own experiences, demonstrating how their decisions are influenced by prior experiences. Women who previously gave birth at home but later chose to have their babies delivered in a hospital, clinics, or polyclinics demonstrate how much they learn and change as they go along.

Mothers discussed how their social networks and communities influenced their choices.

One important reason is the worry that selecting home birth may be met with judgment or rejection from the community, particularly if there are complications. This emphasizes how crucial community views and expectations are when influencing decisions about maternal health. Older participants admit to having given birth at home, but they also accept the advantages of hospital deliveries in today's society (Karanja et al., 2018). In contrast to these findings, a study conducted in rural India (Nair et al., 2012) found that age had no bearing on whether or not a woman chooses to give birth in a health facility.

The demographic dynamics and the sociocultural (the caste system) distinction between India and other developing nations may be to blame for the study's varied findings. However, the majority of the women in the current study said they favor facility deliveries because of their safety. The

larger objective of encouraging skilled attendance during labor and enhancing mother and baby outcomes is aligned with this preference.

The results of the present study agree with those of a study by Lu et al. (2020). They identified several significant barriers preventing rural residents from obtaining healthcare, including inadequate healthcare facilities, distances to healthcare facilities, a lack of effective and efficient transportation systems, inadequate healthcare professionals, and an inability to pay for healthcare services. Similar factors were found to be impeding child health among the poor, especially rural inhabitants, in a study conducted by Adam et al., (2004), and these consequences had an impact on the difference in mortality rates between rural and urban areas. As transportation is a major barrier to receiving health services, this is worse for rural

residents who live beside water bodies and travel to district capitals.

4.5 Experiences of Mothers with regards to the Free Maternal Healthcare Policy

According to several mothers, the implementation of the Free Maternal Health Policy has led to a significant decrease in home births. They attribute this trend to the benefits of facility births, including the ease of identifying difficulties and the availability of medical interventions. Women are encouraged to opt for hospital deliveries due to the guarantee of safer birthing experiences that are easily accessible in the community's newly constructed healthcare facilities.

However, it's important to acknowledge that not all women share the same perspective. Some argue that they haven't noticed a noticeable reduction in home deliveries. They maintain that individual preferences, customs, and the use of regional herbs still influence some women's decisions to give

birth at home. These divergent viewpoints suggest that the impact of the policy may vary depending on personal circumstances, local customs, and regional disparities.

In conclusion, while some mothers report seeing a dramatic decline in home births, others highlight the continuing importance of customs and individual preferences (Tafere et al., 2018). These divergent opinions highlight the need for a nuanced assessment of policy impact and the realization that decisions on maternal healthcare may differ across communities and regions in Ghana.

4.6 Effects of the Free Maternal Health Policy on Home Deliveries

The Free Maternal Health Policy's implementation has, according to women, significantly improved the safety of birthing. They credit the policy's emphasis on skilled facility deliveries for this increased safety. Home deliveries were once thought to be dangerous, especially if difficulties occurred.

With the policy in place, women feel more secure knowing that healthcare facilities are staffed with qualified experts who can handle unforeseen circumstances (Gabrysch & Campbell, 2009). Mothers highlight cases of complicated childbirths and cesarean procedures where having access to medical facilities and experienced staff was essential to ensuring the safety of both mother and child. The accessibility of emergency care in healthcare facilities is emphasized as a crucial element in enhancing safety. The women acknowledge that the heightened safety measures have resulted in better mother and child health outcomes (Ghana Statistical Service, Ghana Health Service, & ICF, 2018). It is thought to be a big advantage to have emergency-ready hospitals and medical facilities close by. This accessibility guarantees that issues can be resolved quickly, lowering the possibility of

unfavorable results (Gabrysch & Campbell, 2009).

Mothers frequently comment on the fact that there has been a noticeable rise in the number of hospitals and other healthcare facilities offering services for maternal care. It is important to emphasize the convenience of having healthcare facilities close by since it enables pregnant women to seek care and prenatal exams as soon as they feel any discomfort or have concerns about their pregnancy (WHO, 2016). The women once more shared their experiences on routine prenatal checkups at medical facilities.

The results of the present study agree with those of numerous other studies on the subject. For instance, it has been determined that using facility-based delivery services is one of the best and most effective strategies for lowering maternal fatalities (Gangtaba et al., 2021). These researchers claim that it helps ensure healthy delivery and reduces

both real and potential difficulties that can result in maternal mortality. In poor nations, the use of skilled birth attendants (SBAs), antenatal care (ANC), postnatal care (PNC), and emergency obstetric and newborn care (EmONC) improves mother and neonatal health and reduces mortality (Yaya et al., 2018). According to Press (2017), if all women had access to treatment options for preventing or treating pregnancy- and birth-related problems, at least 75% of maternal fatalities could be avoided. Again, Rawe (2011) argues that it is harmful for women to put their lives and the lives of their unborn children in danger by giving birth on their own. Around the world, 48 million women give birth without the assistance of a medical expert, and during childbirth, 358,000 maternal deaths and 814,000 neonatal deaths take place.

Women in the current study agree that the Free Maternal Health Policy has significantly

increased pregnant women's access to high-quality medical treatment (Sartorius & Drain, 2016). Due to their rural locations and the associated problems, hospitals used to be difficult for many women to attend, especially during emergencies. However, since the policy's introduction, expecting moms now have easier access to local healthcare facilities. The accessibility to high-quality care has significantly improved as a result of healthcare facilities' proximity to communities (Ekpenyong, Bond, & Matheson, 2019).

The women in the current study stress the need to stop relying entirely on traditional birth attendants and conventional treatments. They understand the value of cutting-edge medical techniques and qualified medical personnel in ensuring safer outcomes for both moms and infants. The availability of qualified medical staff and experienced doctors is regarded as a major benefit of

choosing facility delivery. If pregnant women had access to a skilled birth attendant, such as a doctor, nurse, or midwife during delivery, many mother and child mortalities as well as birth problems may be prevented or successfully handled (Rawe, 2011). However, the services of Traditional Birth Attendants (TBAs) are still preferred to Skilled Birth Attendants (SBAs) because they are friendlier and understand the needs of women during childbirth (Tafere et al., 2018).

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

According to the study, an overwhelmingly high percentage of women - 98.4% - choose to give birth in medical facilities such as hospitals rather than non-facility deliveries like home births. This trend is largely attributed to the Free Maternal Health Policy, which has successfully encouraged expectant mothers to opt for medical facilities for delivery. While a small percentage of women

still prefer alternative methods, it's clear that additional measures may be necessary to ensure equal access to top-quality maternal healthcare services. The policy has led to a decline in home deliveries, as women increasingly choose hospital births for their convenience, access to medical interventions, and prompt identification of complications. However, some women still prefer home births due to personal choice, cultural practices, and the use of traditional remedies. It is important to note that the impact of the policy varies depending on individual experiences, local traditions, and regional disparities. Overall, the policy has made high-quality medical care more accessible and cheaper, encouraging pregnant mothers to select facility birth. With a growing acceptance of contemporary healthcare procedures and the significance of qualified healthcare workers, there has been a shift

toward experienced professional healthcare practitioners.

Limitations of the Study

The scope of this study was restricted to assessing the effects of the free maternal healthcare policy on home birth in the Bekwai Municipality due to the complexity of the issue. Since the study was restricted to a small locality, generalizations about its results are not possible. This investigation will be completed in a constrained amount of time with constrained personnel and financial resources. Another limitation is researcher bias, which can occur not only due to the selective collection and recording of data but also during the process of analysis and interpretation (Saldaña, 2013). A researcher's familiarity with the field may lead them to overlook certain uncertainties and nuances in collected data due to their inherent understanding of the research setting. However, familiarity with the setting

can be useful for validating responses and findings (Slettebø, 2020).

Conclusion

In conclusion, nearly all mothers (98.4%) chose facility delivery, indicating that Ghana's Free Maternal Health Policy had a major impact on maternal healthcare decisions. This strategy has improved safety, relieved financial burdens, improved access

to healthcare, and shifted the focus to qualified healthcare professionals. The benefits of facility delivery are further increased by the availability of cutting-edge medical equipment in healthcare facilities. Although there are still some regional variances and difficulties, this program has significantly improved maternal and child health outcomes in Ghana

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